

IUC 09: Infrastructure interfaces with condensed matter physics (collaboration with FAIRmat)

IUC members: Markus Kühbach¹, Sarath Menon², Alaukik Saxena², Mariano Forti³, Pavlína Kružíková⁴, Thomas Hammerschmidt³, Claudia Draxl¹, Tilmann Hickel⁵

10.5281/zenodo.12594062

1 Physics Department and CSMB, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Berlin

2 Max-Planck-Institut für Nachhaltige Materialien GmbH, Düsseldorf

3 ICAMS, Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Bochum

4 BAM, Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung, Berlin

IUC09 started its activities in 2023. Since then, we have implemented examples of how software tools developed within the NFDI-MatWerk and the FAIRmat consortia can be interfaced functionally and become interoperable semantically to build services for users of both consortia and the global community. IUC09 investigates the use case of how exemplar workflows from the atom probe tomography scientific community can be documented using comprehensive contextualization. Example workflows have been set up for how to process atomic positions into geometrical descriptions of microstructural features such as interfaces formed by phase boundaries with full documentation of intermediate results and making numerical quantities accessible.

The work is mainly pursued via asynchronous software development using Github and Anaconda, supplemented by monthly online meetings of the team members. So far, the team of IUC09 has delivered the following results and software products (with respective links pointing the reader to details):

1. Refactoring of the paraprobe-toolbox software and releasing on Anaconda package manager: <https://anaconda.org/conda-forge/paraprobe>
2. Refactoring of the CompositionSpace software and releasing on Anaconda package manager: <https://anaconda.org/conda-forge/compositionspace>
3. Implementation of the workflows for both software tools using pyiron via exemplary binder and docker containers that are offered to the public on national and international meetings.
4. Development of atom-probe-domain-specific extensions of the semantic file format NeXus for both tools: https://fairmat-nfdi.github.io/nexus_definitions/classes/contributed_definitions/apm-structure.html#apm-structure
5. Development of atom-probe-specific customizations of the research data management software framework NOMAD Oasis to read, analyze, and visualize content produced with the tools above-mentioned: https://gitlab.mpcdf.mpg.de/nomad-lab/nomad-FAIR/-/merge_requests/1829

In summary, the value added to the MatWerk community is the standardization of software tools such that the exchange of data, metadata, semantic data, and concepts for data processing between two NFDI consortia is ensured without a loss of information. More specifically, open-source software tools for the analysis of APT data have been considered. Furthermore, the extension and interoperability of the two tools with one another and to the semantic file format NeXus has been achieved. Example code offers value as it shows how these tools can be orchestrated with the Integrated Development Environment pyiron to generate reusable workflows for processing atom probe data to build upon that. These achievements are offered as standalone tools. The full potential of this joint effort of the two consortia is released by coupling to a research data management system.

For the remaining funding period we plan to summarize these results into a joint publication. Thereafter, we will explore how to connect the results of the current semantic description that uses NeXus to other semantic activities within NFDI-MatWerk, FAIRmat, and the wider NFDI. One connection to explore here is to the Open Crystallographic Defects Ontologies of IUC17 to strengthen the semantic reasoning capabilities.

This publication was written by the NFDI consortia NFDI-MatWerk and FAIRmat in the context of the work of the association German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) e.V.. NFDI is financed by the Federal Republic of Germany and the 16 federal states and funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBWF) – funding code M532701 / the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under the National Research Data Infrastructure – NFDI 38/1 – project number 460247524, and project number 460197019 (FAIRmat). Furthermore, we acknowledge financial support by the German Research Foundation (DFG) through project A4 and C1 of the collaborative research center SFB/TR 103 (project number 190389738).